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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

There is an increasing recognition of the importance of establishing standards for environmental monitoring applied to the wave energy industry to understand the potential impacts of a device in early stages of its development. This report presents a standard method for Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), including a Socioeconomic Impact Analysis (SEIA) for wave energy projects. An exhaustive literature review was carried out on previous EIAs for similar installations, leading to the identification of a set of receptors and stressors potentially related to the development of nearshore wave energy devices. Their interaction was then crossed in a Summary Impact Matrix. The proposed method builds upon this literature and is divided into 3 main steps including prioritization of the most significant impacts, mitigation measures to be implemented and monitoring techniques to be carried out to validate the preliminary impacts' analysis. An Adaptive Management (AM) approach is adopted to manage the project impacts regarding mitigation measures' adaptation and monitoring plan review. The present model is intended to work as a guideline for regulators and managers to apply in nearshore wave energy devices and will be further validated through its application on the final MegaRoller device, an oscillating wave surge converter (OWSC) technology currently in development phase. The method developed under this study represents a significant step towards the standardization of EIA for nearshore wave energy devices. The data collected for the elaboration of this framework provides a means for deepening our knowledge of the potential environmental and socioeconomic impacts of nearshore wave energy projects, allowing regulators and managers for better decision-making. In addition, this report sets the basis for the development of a decision-making tool on the delineation of best monitoring activities schedule and planning, which will later be validated through its application to the final MegaRoller design.

List of Acronyms

EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
SEIA	Socioeconomic Impact Analysis
AM	Adaptive Management
OWSC	Oscillating Wave Surge Converter
WEC	Wave Energy Converter
MSP	Marine Spatial Planning
EMEC	European Marine Energy Center
EMF	Electromagnetic Field
MRE	Marine Renewable Energy
ADCP	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature, Depth
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
HPLC	High Performance Liquid Chromatography

1 INTRODUCTION

There is an increasing recognition of the importance of establishing standards for environmental monitoring so an early knowledge on the magnitude of the potential environmental impacts during the testing of commercial scale wave technologies should be considered. This ensures that the marine energy industry considers environmental implications of its projects in early stages of design and development which will result in the adoption of best practices.

The Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) is a stepwise approach already implemented in several countries' legislation and it usually integrates projects' consenting process. However, there is a significant variation in EIA procedures which is directly linked with legal, policy and institutional frameworks in different countries. The SOWFIA project (EU, 2018) carried out a review on the licensing procedures which showed the EIA process for ocean energy in Europe still lacks a streamlined framework and concludes that only through increasing knowledge can the EIA process be more specifically adapted to ocean energy developments. The consenting of offshore renewable energy is often considered the main non-technical barrier to the development of the sector as there are several uncertainties related to the potential environmental impacts of emerging technologies. Based on this, the RiCORE project¹ established a risk-based approach to consenting where the level of survey requirement is based on the environmental sensitivity of the site, the risk profile of the technology and the scale of the proposed project.

The fact that wave energy projects have unique characteristics, different from any other marine projects, results in a lack of methodological approaches for environmental and socio-economic impacts evaluation. The existing information focus mainly on environmental results for prototype or small array projects and, in many cases, the small scale of these projects doesn't justify the need for a full EIA process. EQUIMAR project² has proposed guidance to the process of environmental impact assessment although assuming the early stage of development of the technology linked to a high level of uncertainty.

A new standard model for EIA and monitoring is therefore strongly needed for wave energy projects. This report reviews on the most relevant nearshore installations and proposes an environmental and socioeconomic impact assessment standardised model to work as a guideline for regulators and managers in nearshore devices, adopting an Adaptive Management (AM) approach. The model presented here is based on an exhaustive literature survey regarding environmental effects of nearshore installations (e.g. wave energy projects, pontoons and other artificial hard structures, aquaculture cages, etc.) to comprehensively address stressors, receptors and effects of this kind of structures and broaden the EIA model application. The results of this survey are presented in this document and include an analysis of the sensitivity of nearshore areas from an ecological point of view (Chapter 2), a description of the features of different types of nearshore installations (Chapter 3) and the identification of nearshore wave energy devices potential environmental effects or impacts from a stressor/receptor perspective (Chapter 4). Mitigation measures (Chapter 5) as well as monitoring protocols and the starting point for the delineation of monitoring activities (Chapter 6), usually applied to the most relevant impacts (classified from negligible

¹ <http://ricore-project.eu/>

² <http://www.equimar.org/>

to major), have also been reviewed and summarised to inform further model application. The EIA model is proposed under Chapter 7 for effects evaluation and prioritization of a specific project, which is linked to a stepwise approach for the selection of appropriate mitigation and monitoring protocols. Final remarks on model application are added at the end of the document (Chapter 8) to highlight some aspects of the application of standard methodologies and prepare the EIA /SEIA model application to the MegaRoller final design (WP5, Task 5.4).

1.1 Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) – general aspects

EIA is an environmental management instrument implemented worldwide that ensures that the environmental implications of a certain action are considered before decision making in a given project. The general main steps of the EIA process are shown in Figure 1.1. In Europe, the majority of MRE developments require EIA to ensure the effects of the development on the environment, biological and physical processes (Leeney et al., 2014). Wave Energy Converter (WEC) projects in full scale are expected to be subject to an EIA process. On the other hand, test sites and small-scale demonstration projects may not be required to carry out a full-scale EIA process since pre-consenting (performed during test site licensing) is usually available.

Figure 1.1: Environmental Impact Assessment approach: theoretical steps.

Screening is the first step of the EIA process and consists on deciding on whether an EIA is required. If this stage leads to the conclusion that an EIA is required, the next stage is the scoping phase. This stage identifies the issues that are likely to be of most importance during the EIA so that the study focuses on the significant aspects and avoids time consuming activities. Baseline characterization gives information about the reference conditions of the site where the project will take place, on an environmental and

socioeconomic level, and are the basis to predict potential impacts. The identification and prediction of impacts contribute for the delineation of mitigation measures. The mitigation process refers to methods of action that need to be taken to prevent, minimize and compensate for the predicted adverse effects of the project or to enhance its positive effects. Finally, a monitoring plan should be drawn for all project phases (from preparation to decommissioning) considering all the information obtained in the previous steps. Monitoring an effect or an impact means that the monitoring plan must be designed to measure change against some baseline condition or management objective. It is a key step to validate and change initial EIA findings. Public involvement throughout the whole process ensures all stakeholders are actively participating in the EIA process and contributing to decision making.

Since the scoping is done in an early stage of the project, mitigation measures can be further studied and be used as an input to design choices and operational procedures and logistics that lead to a reduction in the environmental impact of the project.

One of the approaches that have been proposed for the impacts assessment of wave energy projects is the identification of stressors which refer to any single characteristic or activity of an ocean energy project, and receptors, defined as the ecosystem elements that may be affected by a stressor (Iglesias et al., 2018). During the identification of potential impacts, the effects of such stressors on the receptors are then quantified based on experience related with similar projects or simply based on expert knowledge regarding the sensitivity of the site and project characteristics. Most of the times information is not available and thus the decision-making on approving a project needs to be risk based relying on the implementation of mitigation measures and on the results of monitoring activities. An AM approach should therefore be applied to manage project impacts in terms of mitigation measures' adaptation and monitoring plan review.

AM is an iterative process that promotes decision-making, which can be adjusted in the face of uncertainties as outcomes from management and other events become better understood (Hanna et al., 2016). This learn-based management approach leads to improved decision-making for a better management of the environment together with the goals set. AM has been widely used in MRE projects in the United States, e.g. Ocean Power Technologies applied AM for their Reedsport Wave Park to reduce negative environmental and socioeconomic effects, to alter management and monitoring activities as new data were collected, and to assess the potential for a larger project (FERC, 2010).

2 SENSITIVITY OF MARINE NEARSHORE AREAS

The nearshore environment is generally defined as the area encompassing the transition from subtidal marine habitats to associated upland systems. Within the marine system, the nearshore subsystem extends from the landward limit of the Marine System to the 30 meters depth contour (Figure 2.1: The marine system. Adapted from Federal Geographic Data Committee (2012). Figure 2.1). This limit represents an ecologically significant depth to which water column and benthic processes are strongly coupled in the nearshore subsystem. The marine offshore subsystem extends from the 30 meters depth contour to the continental shelf break, generally occurring between 100 - 200 meters depth (FERC, 2010).

Figure 2.1: The marine system. Adapted from Federal Geographic Data Committee (2012).

The shallow, coastal regions of the oceans are geologically young and vastly dynamic areas, with changing biological, chemical and geological features and highly productive ecosystems. In the context of ocean energy, the representative biotopes of areas with high energetic wave climate are hard or soft bottoms, kelp forest/park and landfall extensions.

The assessment of the sensitivity in a given area is an important stage in an EIA report, to understand the natural variability of the environment, as well as its vulnerabilities to given pressures, so that a prediction of potential impacts can be listed. The sensitivity analysis should therefore consider both environmental (biological and physical) factors and the socioeconomic aspects specific to a site.

2.1 Environmental Factors

These areas provide a variety of ecosystems services including: i) nursery grounds for a wide variety of marine invertebrates and fishes (e.g., crabs and salmon), ii) nesting and pupping habitats for many pelagic marine predators (e.g., sea bird nesting colonies), iii) important feeding habitats for high trophic level pelagic predators (e.g., killer whales), iv) habitat for resident nearshore species (e.g., shorebirds, sea ducks, nearshore fishes and marine invertebrates (Ballachey et al., 2015). Coastal regions also play a crucial role as migration passages for a vast number of marine species, since they represent a strong linkage connection between the open ocean to freshwater ecosystems. The canopy forming kelps and eel grass beds found in the nearshore provide primary production and structure to nursery habitats. They can also dissipate wave energy thus reducing coastal erosion, and serve as a carbon 'sink' able of storing significant amounts of CO₂ (Wilmers et al., 2012).

Regarding the ecosystem physical characteristics, the nearshore wave resource is less uniform than its offshore counterpart due to the interaction with the seabed. When changing from deep waters to intermediate or transitional waters, the wave is constrained vertically by the seabed as it continues to

propagate towards the shore. This event gives rise to several physical phenomena, which affects wave properties except for the wave period which remains unchanged. Hereupon, nearshore spatial variability in wave energy increases with irregularity of the bathymetry (Simas et al., 2013).

Other particularity of coastal areas is the energy transfer from the wind as waves propagate towards the shoreline (Iglesias et al., 2018). Wind stress also drives the upwelling event in coastal areas. Thermal characteristics of the upwelled water masses can influence warming trends in nearshore regions, with potential to buffer the effects of global warming nearshore, with wide oceanographic, climatic, and biogeographic implications (Varela et al., 2018).

In coastal zones, hydrodynamic processes are the driving force of sediment transport and evolution of the seabed (Sawczyński and Kaczmarek, 2014). These coastal processes include erosion, transport and deposition of sediments, essential for long shore drift material and ultimately beach morphology, also nutrients, gases and food transport for some species and distribution of juvenile stages reliant on that transport (Greaves et al., 2016). Any disturbance on the seabed may increase sediment suspension and water column turbidity, decreasing light penetration and interfering with primary production.

2.2 Socioeconomic Factors

Marine and particularly coastal ecosystems provide a wide range of services to human society including supporting, regulating, recreational and provisioning services (UNEP-WCMC, 2011), which is the reason why coastal regions are usually more densely urbanized and have a more developed economy than inland regions (Yi et al., 2018). The main socio-economic activities identified in coastal regions include fisheries, navigation, tourism, engineering interventions, aquaculture, and wave and wind energy.

Human activities within the marine environment have proven to arise several pressures on coastal habitats, including loss of habitat, habitat change by altering dominant oceanographic conditions and the physical and chemical properties of the seawater. In addition, these changes affect the distribution and extent of habitat as well as the structure of biological communities. Overall, many ecosystems have undergone a major structural shift in the past decades due to the combined effects of human intervention and changing environmental conditions (MacLean et al., 2013).

Taking the environmental and socioeconomic aspects of nearshore areas into account, the complexity and variability of these ecosystems is clear. Sensitivity can be defined as the intolerance of a habitat, community or species to damage, or death, from an external factor (Tyler-Walters and Jackson, 1999). There is an increasing interest in identifying sensitive and vulnerable marine areas as a valuable tool in coastal and marine management and conservation efforts. Nearshore habitats are highly vulnerable to natural pressures. Given its proximity to upland activities, the nearshore is particularly exposed to multiple stressors facing multiple challenges associated with increased human impacts, including climate change. Some key threats to nearshore ecosystems include: i) habitat loss by coastal development, dredging, filling, draining; ii) habitat alteration by hardening of shorelines, fragmentation (particularly for nearshore nurseries); iii) altered freshwater and saltwater flows; iv) loss of water clarity (threatening kelps and coral reefs); v) eutrophication (leading to low oxygen conditions and increased alga blooms); vi) invasive species; vii) overfishing and bycatch (leading to population loss and altered community structure) and viii) trawling and other fishing gear impacts that alter or destroy habitat (Nursery Roles Working Group, 2003).

3 IDENTIFICATION AND DESCRIPTION OF NEARSHORE ACTIVITIES AND INSTALLATIONS

Besides navigation and fisheries, a range of other economic activities are currently competing for the use of the nearshore areas around the globe, calling for the increasing need to manage these waters more coherently through Marine Spatial Planning (MSP). Among other benefits, MSP reduces conflicts between sectors, creates synergies between different activities and protects the environment through early identification of impact and opportunities for multiple use of space. This section describes the main nearshore installations and activities identified in the literature: fisheries, navigation, aquaculture, seawalls, and wind and wave power generation (table 3.1).

Table 3.1: Summary of key effects on marine nearshore economic sectors.

Sector	Key Effects
Fisheries	Overfishing; Change of population’s dynamics; Disruption of seabed; Water quality damage
Navigation	Chemical pollution; Noise disturbance; Loss of habitat
Aquaculture	Biological pollution; Organic pollution; Chemical pollution; habitat change; over-exploitation of marine resources
Seawalls	Change of hydrodynamic system and sediment transport; Loss of habitat; Possible habitat assemblages
Offshore Wind Energy	Changes of the hydrodynamic system and sediment transport; Loss of habitat; Interactions with benthic communities and surface animals
Wave Energy	Changes of the hydrodynamic system and sediment transport; Loss of habitat; Interactions with benthic communities and surface animals

3.1 Fisheries

The fishery sector plays a vital socio-economic function as a source of food and income as many communities rely on fish as their main source of animal protein (UNEP, 2006). Although its significance to human society is invaluable, it is important to acknowledge the highly negative effects of fishing in the marine communities such as over-fishing, bycatch (incidental take), habitat damage and indirect effects of the reduction of target species involving food web complications.

The most relevant effects of the capture fishing sector to this study are the direct and indirect impacts on benthic habitats and associated fauna and flora (Piet et al., 2000). Bottom-contacting gears applied in this industry can directly change populations dynamics and physically damage (abrasion) seabed habitats. Indirect impacts on the benthic communities derive from long term changes to the water turbidity and sedimentation, and include effects in food web interactions, recruitment, nursery and feeding habitats.

3.2 Navigation

Vessel activity is practised nowadays either for commercial, fishery or military purposes. The practice of this activity in coastal areas carries several impacts on the ecosystem including chemical releases from

antifouling paints, disturbance of the ecosystem equilibrium due to dredging activities (underwater excavation which includes excavation, transport and disposal of sediments) either for aiding ship navigation or to expand ports and harbours and also noise pollution caused by active sonars used in shipping and naval sonar operations (Telegdi et al., 2016; Manap and Voulvoulis, 2015).

Biofouling consequences for shipping include speed reduction, higher fuel consumption, and corrosion increase. To tackle this problem, antifouling paints have been developed to prevent the attachment of unwanted organisms. The persistence of some of these compounds in the water is highly toxic for the surrounding environment (Telegdi et al., 2016).

Acoustic pollution is of great concern to marine life, as many species use sound for predation, communication, navigation, reproduction and feeding. Some massive cetacean stranding events throughout the last decades have been linked to naval sonar activities (Balcomb and Claridge, 2001; van Bree and Kristensen, 1974). The effects of active sonar on marine mammals have subsequently become a major welfare and conservation issue (Marine Mammal Commission, 2007; Weilgart, 2007).

3.3 Aquaculture

Over the past 30 years, global production of cultivated aquatic food developed tremendously with hundreds of different animal species such as finfish, crustaceans, and molluscs being produced in aquaculture systems (FAO, 2014). Aquaculture provides several economic and other benefits, however, its practice without adequate environmental safeguards can cause serious environmental degradation such as biological pollution, demand of fish feed resources, organic pollution and eutrophication, chemical pollution and habitat modification (Goldburg et al., 2001; Ottinger et al., 2016).

Biological pollution is likely to happen when fish escape from the culture facilities, thus enabling them to harm wild fish populations through competition, interbreeding and even spreading diseases or parasites (Finstad et al., 2001). In the future, farming transgenic or genetically modified fish may rise concerns about biological pollution (Hedrick, 2001).

Aquaculture systems contribute to organic pollution by nutrient loading through discharges of organism's waste or uneaten feed with subsequent release of high amounts of nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus) and suspended solids into nearby coastal waters (Islam et al., 2004) which in turn leads to eutrophication (Carrasquilla-Henao et al., 2013) and algal blooms.

The excessive use of chemicals (antibiotics, pesticides, fertilizers) also enriches waters with nutrients and pollutants (bacteria, viruses and other toxic compounds) (Sohel and Ullah, 2012), contaminating natural coastal waters if directly discharged.

Finally, regarding habitat modification, some facilities attract marine predators, who can suffer from accidental entanglement (Wursig and Gailey, 2002). These installations can also obstruct the species' use of the natural surroundings.

3.4 Seawalls

Worldwide, coastal communities face shoreline modification events, either due to global warming, sea level rise or anthropogenic activities, resulting in widespread modification of sandy beach ecosystems (McLachlan and Defeo, 2017). The society's response to beach erosion and shoreline retreat relies on

engineering interventions that place armouring structures on beaches (Pilkey and Cooper, 2014). Breakwaters are shore-parallel structures designed to resist natural processes and built offshore to reduce wave energy or hold the beach sand in place. The reduction of wave action promotes sediment deposition shoreward of the structure, called the sheltered area, where the sediment is retained as the coastline material is deposited (Birben et al., 2007). Armouring structures alter the natural hydrodynamic system of waves and currents, affecting the sand transport rates and controlling therefore the erosion-accretion dynamics of beaches (Miles et al., 2001). Environmental impacts can include flanking erosion of shorelines adjacent to those protected by engineering structures, passive erosion in armoured beaches and significant habitat changes (Defeo et al., 2009). On the other side, they can also serve as viable habitats for biological communities (Liversage and Chapman, 2018).

3.5 Wind Energy

Wind power is generally recognized as one of the leading renewable energy technologies. The concept of offshore wind installations developed, as the wind is stronger and more consistent in the open sea (GE Energy, 2002).

The potential environmental impacts associated with the offshore wind include the influence of the installation phase on the hydrology and sediment conditions (physical properties), which will consequently affect the marine communities and thereafter the whole ecosystem sector (Draget, 2014). The development of offshore wind entails some loss of natural seabed areas. Also, negative impacts on marine life may arise through underwater noise, where the acoustic emissions into the body of water, particularly on construction phase, may arise lethal effects or damages in hearing to marine mammals and fishes, and through artificial magnetic and/or electrical fields of the cable connections, which may interfere with the species' orientation. Moreover, offshore wind power brings several potential impacts on birds, including displacement from existing habitats involving nesting sites and/or foraging areas, risk of collision with wind turbine blades and migration barriers. On the other hand, during the operation phase, they often end up functioning as artificial reefs, leading to an increase in the species' diversity.

3.6 Wave Energy

The potential associated with ocean energy technology, in terms of security of supply, economic growth and reduction of CO₂ emissions has fostered an increasing interest in supporting the development of ocean energy globally (Badcock-Broe et al., 2014).

However, the effects that wave energy converters will have on physical and biological processes and their impact on the marine environment are yet to be fully determined (Leeney et al., 2014). Margheritini et. al (2011) stated that while some of the effects of introducing MRE installations in the marine environment will be the same regardless the type of installation, other effects will be device specific.

As it has been established in this report, nearshore installations are the centre of attention, hence the focus on the interactions between these devices in the coastal environment. There are two sets of nearshore environmental impacts associated with WEC development: direct impacts due to the construction at or near the shoreline, either for cables, stability elements or the installation of the device itself, and indirect impacts caused by reduction in wave energy reaching the shore and nearshore waters (Nelson et al., 2008).

4 WAVE ENERGY STRESSORS, RECEPTORS AND EFFECTS/IMPACTS

According to Boehlert and Gill (2010), stressors are features of the environment that may change, in this case, with the implementation of nearshore installations; receptors are ecosystem elements with potential for some form of response to the stressor; and effects or impacts (when severity, intensity or duration of the effect needs to be quantified) are consequences of the stressors on the receptors. An exhaustive literature survey was carried out to identify and evaluate the main effects of nearshore installations on the receiving environment based on stressors and receptors, focusing mainly on wave energy developments. Data were organised in three main factors: physical, biological and socio-economic, considering four project development phases: preparation, construction, operation and decommissioning. Physical, biological and socioeconomic key effects were evaluated through a ranking classification criteria adapted from EMEC guidelines (EMEC, 2013) comprising 6 levels of magnitude of impact (**Error! Reference source not found.** and Table 4.2). It is important to note that an effect is later referred as impact when upon its characterisation a magnitude value is assigned (Shumchenia et al., 2012). It is also relevant to stress that, besides construction, operation and decommissioning phases, the preparation phase also constitutes an essential part of project development, providing as well potential impacts to be considered. Summary impact matrices are presented in the following sections. Whenever a key effect was found in the literature to have two different magnitude levels, the range of classifications are represented in the matrix.

Table 4.1 - Classification environmental aspects.

Magnitude of Impact		Description
	Major	Degradation to the quality or availability of habitats and/or wildlife with recovery taking more than 2 years
	Moderate	Change in habitats or species beyond natural variability with good recovery potentially within 2 years
	Minor	Change from baseline conditions measurable but within scale of natural variability
	Negligible	Change in habitats or species within scope of existing variability and difficult to measure or observe
	No Interaction	None
	<i>Positive</i>	<i>An enhancement of ecosystem or popular parameter</i>

Table 4.2: Classification of socioeconomic aspects.

Magnitude of Impact		Description
Major		Change to commercial activity leading to a loss of income or opportunity beyond normal business variability/risk. Potential short-term effect upon public health/well-being, real risk of injury
Moderate		Change to commercial activity leading to a loss of income or opportunity beyond normal business variability/risk. Possible, but not likely effect upon public health/well-being, remote risk of injury.
Minor		Possible nuisance to other activities and some minor influence on income or opportunity. Nuisance, but no lasting effect upon public health/well-being.
Negligible		Noticed by, but not a nuisance to other commercial activities. No discernible effects upon the health and well-being of the public
No Interaction		None
Positive		<i>Benefits to local community</i>

4.1 Physical Factors

The wave and currents regime is a primary determinant of nearshore environments, which influences or controls the circulation patterns, the impact forces on plants and animals, the erosion of sandy and rocky shorelines, the fluxes of sediment and particulate organic matter, the fluxes of pollutants and nutrients, the turbulence and organism-scale fluxes, the water aeration, the turbidity and light availability, and the sea level setup and flooding (Nelson et al., 2008). Table 4.3 summarizes the effects of nearshore wave energy installations on the physical factor, considering stressors affecting 4 distinct receptors – hydrodynamic system, water column, seabed and shoreline – during the different phases of a project.

Although the physical impacts vary among the different phases of the project, they are expected to be higher during the construction and decommissioning phases, as disturbance of the seabed is greater during these two phases than during the device’s operation. Construction activities for WEC devices require drilling and/or anchoring, installation of mooring systems and transmission cables to the shoreline, and adding the increase in vessel activity, these combined actions will disrupt the seabed, as well as increase sediment suspension and turbidity levels. In terms of water quality, normal activities during construction and decommissioning of the WECs should not cause a pollution event that could affect the water column.

4.1.1 Water quality

It is worth recognising that any construction and decommissioning activity of this nature could have an adverse impact on water quality, due to damage, negligence and/or accidents so preventative mitigation measures are recommended. The principal types of substances that may pose a risk to water quality are mineral oil-based coolants, hydraulic fluids and paintings of devices or vessels, which usually are rapidly dispersed in the immediate water column (Conley et al., 2013). In addition, focusing on floating types of WECs that require cabling associated, cable laying and removal may result a negative impact on water

quality since it would increase the concentrations of arsenic and copper in the near-bed part of the water column, although this usually occurs on a very small scale and the released arsenic and copper would be quickly diluted to acceptable concentrations, with no significant impact predicted (Halcrow Group Limited, 2006).

4.1.2 Wave and currents regime change

Energy extraction must be taken into consideration during the operational phase. Devices that harvest electrical power from waves extract potential or kinetic energy from waves as they pass. This energy extraction will result in a wave shadow behind the device, where wave heights are reduced. This way, the removal of energy from the marine environment is identified as a potential negative effect, as those changes will influence the transport of gases and nutrients, turbulence levels, as well as the sediment transport long shore, and therefore beach morphology. Some case studies on the impact of WECs on nearshore wave climate (Palha et al., 2010; Nørgaard and Andersen, 2015; Millar et al., 2007) confirmed the reduction of wave action, and a few also proved that these technologies are able to reduce erosion at the beach front, providing a certain level of coastal protection (Abanades et al., 2015; Nørgaard and Andersen, 2015; Bergillos et al., 2017).

4.1.3 Disruption of seabed and shoreline morphology

Apart from the shoreline morphology interactions, energy wave harvesting in the nearshore environment is deemed to be compatible, because since these technologies are placed in such highly energetic environments that the localised impact on waves and currents is unlikely to be significant (Aquamarine Power, 2011; PMSS, 2007).

Table 4.3: Summary Impact Matrix for potential physical interactions between nearshore installations and the receiving environment. M: Impact magnitude; NK: no anticipated key effect.

Physical Effects			Receptor							
Development Phase	Activity	Stressor	Hydrodynamic System		Water Column		Seabed		Shoreline	
			Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M
Preparation	Surveying	Sampling, vessel activity and sonar/seismic surveys	NK		Increase in turbidity		Disturbance of seabed morphology		NK	
	Site preparation	Dredging and seabed levelling activities	NK		Increase in turbidity; Deterioration of water quality		Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		Shoreline material removal/addition, affecting local topography	
Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Vessel activity and presence of machinery/equipment	NK		Disruption of pelagic habitats		NK		NK	
	Installation of wave device and support structures	Installation of WEC and piling/drilling activities	NK		Increase in turbidity		Disruption of seabed morphology		NK	
Operation	Device deployment	Physical presence of WEC device and structural components	Reduction of wave action		Turbulence hampered		Disruption of seabed morphology		Erosion reduction of shoreline morphology	
								Change in erosion/deposition patterns		
Decommissioning	Removal of device and structural components	Vessel activity and presence of machinery/equipment	NK		Disruption of pelagic habitats; Increase in turbidity		Disruption of seabed morphology; Deterioration of sediment quality		NK	
All development phases (accidental events)	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	Chemical and oil pollution	NK		Deterioration of water quality		Deterioration of sediment quality		Deterioration of sediment and water quality	
	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	NK		Disruption and littering of surface waters		Disruption of seabed morphology		Disruption and littering of shoreline waters	

4.2 Biological Factors

As mentioned before, coastal habitats are highly productive and harbour an immense biodiversity. The structure of communities is conferred by the way organisms in a community are connected in food webs, where any change can impact the community's dynamics (Valiela, 2013). The introduction of wave energy developments represents several stressors to the surrounding marine environment, which are presented in detail through different stages of the project with resulting key effects in Table 4.4 for the following receptors: benthic community, fish and turtles, marine mammals and birds. To better understand the biological interactions with wave energy power production, the interpretation of the matrix was divided into three main groups of key effects: marine communities and habitat modification, underwater noise disturbance and electromagnetic field (EMF) disturbance.

4.2.1 Marine Communities and Habitat Modification

As previously stated, most of marine species diversity is benthic rather than pelagic, being deeply reliable on physical properties of the environment in terms of nutrition, movement, and productivity (Greaves et al., 2016). As table 5.4 shows, several impacts will materialize on the benthic communities and the water column species (fish, marine mammals) surrounding the site throughout the project development as well as in the water column species.

During the preparatory phase, a removal of seabed habitat is usually needed to carry on to the construction phase, either for the placement of the device itself (immersed type) or the anchors/supports (floating type) or the transmission cables to the shoreline (Aquamarine Power, 2011; PMSS, 2007). These two stages will result in a localized habitat loss and death of benthic organisms. The decommissioning of the device will have similar impacts. Additionally, increased levels of turbidity due to suspension of sediments during construction activities would impact photosynthetic organisms through light availability decrease and therefore reduce local primary productivity and hence the food chain. The magnitude of these effects on the benthic community depends on the duration and intensity of disturbance and the resilience of the local infauna (Drabsch, 2001). Based on the available EIA report data, these impacts are usually considered of minor magnitude, since the area affected is very localised and a fully recovery is likely to happen (Aquamarine Power, 2011; PMSS, 2007). Apart from physio-biological interactions, accidental chemical and oil spillages must once again be considered, not only in the construction and decommissioning stages, but also in the operation of the device, as these products may contaminate and harm marine species.

Wave action and current dynamics are critical aspects for the welfare of benthic marine organisms, as these natural processes influence sediment transport and food availability. This way, wave energy extraction characteristic of operational phase might bring some changes to the ecosystem, although not significant (Aquamarine Power, 2011).

Table 4.4: Summary Impact Matrix for potential biological interactions between nearshore installations and the receiving environment. M: Impact magnitude; NK: no anticipated key effect.

Biological Effects			Receptor							
Development phase	Activity	Stressor	Benthic Communities		Fish & Turtles		Marine Mammals		Birds	
			Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M
Preparation	Surveying	Sampling: coring and grab sampling	Death of organisms	M	NK		NK		NK	
		Noise from vessels and sonar/seismic surveys	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour	M
	Site preparation	Dredging Activities	Productivity reduction; Death of organisms	M	Disruption of behaviour	M	Disruption of behaviour	M	Disruption of behaviour	M
Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Vessel activity; Presence of machinery/equipment	Disruption of behaviour	M	Disruption of behaviour	M	Disruption of behaviour	M	Disruption of behaviour	M
		Noise from vessels	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour; potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour	M
	Installation of wave device and support structures	Installation of WEC; Piling/drilling activities	Productivity reduction; Death of organisms	M	Disruption of behaviour; potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour; potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour	M
		Noise from piling/drilling activities	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour	M
Operation	Device deployment	Physical presence of WEC device and structural components	Reef effects; Increase in productivity and biodiversity	M	Enhancement of reproduction and nursery areas; Increase in food availability	M	Increase in food availability	M	Increase in food availability	M
			Risk of harmful biofouling; Invasive species	M	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment	M	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment	M	Risk of collision, entanglement, entrapment	M
		Noise generation	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour; Potential harm	M	Disruption of behaviour	M
		EMFs	Disruption of	M	Disruption of	M	Disruption of	M	NK	

			behaviour		behaviour		behaviour		
Decommissioning	Removal of device and structural components	Vessel activity; Presence of machinery/equipment	Loss of biomass and biodiversity locally enhanced		Disruption of behaviour		Disruption of behaviour		Disruption of behaviour
		Noise from vessels	Disruption of behaviour; potential harm		Disruption of behaviour; potential harm		Disruption of behaviour; potential harm		Disruption of behaviour
All development phases (accidental events)	Chemical / oil / fuel spill	Chemical and oil pollution	Potential toxic response		Potential toxic response		Potential toxic response		Potential toxic response
	Loss of equipment / structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	Disruption of behaviour; potential harm through collision		Disruption of behaviour; potential harm through collision and entanglement		Disruption of behaviour; potential harm through collision and entanglement		Potential harm through collision and entanglement

Regarding the positive impacts anticipated, the WEC can function as an artificial reef. As it is a fixed structure, it will attract fish and shellfish and can increase the amount of species in its vicinity. (Langhamer, 2016; Aquamarine Power, 2011; PMSS, 2007; Want et al., 2017). This phenomenon has already been observed in Peniche, Portugal, where the WaveRoller device was operating between 2012 and 2014. The introduction of new artificial hard substratum gives opportunity for benthos to colonize, leading to an increase in biomass and biodiversity, hence promotion of the ecosystem and the food web (Greaves et al., 2016). It is crucial, however, to clarify if the habitat enhancement will not disturb the normal operation of the WEC or disrupt the productivity ratio in the area (Want et al., 2017). Biofouling, considered positive from a certain ecological and economic perspective, may affect the efficiency of wave power generation (Langhamer, 2016). While this gain of biodiversity could lead to a more diverse natural community than the pre-existing through the attraction of larger predators such as birds, fish and marine mammals, it also may become habitat for invasive species. Exotic species invasion may significantly affect habitat structure, native community composition, local biodiversity, food web structure and subsequently ecosystem services (Greaves et al., 2016).

4.2.2 Collision

The physical presence of the WEC device and underwater elements might also pose risks of collision, entanglement or even entrapment to marine mammals, diving birds and fish (Wilson et al. 2006). Collision risks for surfacing mammals and birds will depend on how aware they are of the presence of the structures. On the other hand, little is known about the risk of collision between fish and underwater devices (Wilson et al., 2006). Although this event has not been yet observed and it is assumed to be unlikely to happen, disturbance and collision are considered one of the most concerned issues related to ocean energy (Margheritini et al., 2011). Moreover, the development may give rise to barrier effects, preventing the use of the habitat as breeding or feeding areas, as well as increasing animal's consumption of energy reserves during migration due to avoidance reactions.

4.2.3 Underwater Noise Disturbance

Marine animals take advantage of sound propagation conditions in marine environments for communication, social interaction, orientation, predation, and evasion, being this capability of detecting and emitting sounds variable by frequency and amplitude. MRE devices generate noise and vibrations, both in the air and underwater, through construction activities and device operation, and since acoustic signals can travel longer distances underwater, marine animals may be affected by noise pollution (Greaves et al., 2016). Marine mammals are particularly acoustic sensitive and rely on sound to survive, hence the focus on the effects provoked by MRE on these species. A certain concern is also taken on marine birds, as their behaviour on landing/roosting/breeding and migrating patterns may be changed due to noise generation (Wilson et al., 2006; Greaves et al., 2016).

Among other factors, the acoustic impact depends on spatial relationships between the sound source and the receptor, its sensitivity, received exposure level, duration and duty cycle of the sound (Cruz et al., 2015).

The main effects that have been observed in marine mammal species due to noise pollution are behavioural modifications (avoidance, attraction, dive behaviour, prey hunt, etc.), auditory masking, hearing injury, and, in severe situations, death (Southall et al., 2007; Iglesias et al., 2018). Injury is considered an elevation of the hearing threshold to a specific frequency, which can be temporary (reversible) or permanent (irreversible).

Noise impacts are predicted as significantly higher during construction and decommissioning activities, as well as during preparatory sonar/seismic surveys. Although there is not enough data on sonar surveys in the context of renewable energy, data on sonar operations for other purposes have predicted serious

effects on marine mammals in nearshore areas (Weilgart, 2007). Thomsen et al. (2015) revealed that the noise levels generated during construction of offshore wind farms, especially from impact pile driving, exceeded regulatory thresholds established, but infer that the resulting levels for MRE devices installation are likely to be less than those from offshore wind.

Once the construction activities are completed, the effects are reduced, yet, noise disturbance during operation phase can still be expected, although with a lesser extent. The long-term effects of the displacement of organisms due to sound fields are a significant data gap in this matter.

A few assessments on underwater noise disturbance by wave energy projects have been done. Their review showed a consistent evaluation on nearshore wave projects impacts on marine life. The Oyster 2 Array project assessed the overall level of impact significance for marine mammals in this matter as minor, by modelling underwater sound propagation from drilling pile/monopile foundations and anchor drilling operations (Aquamarine Power, 2011). Similarly, the SURGE project concluded that the WaveRoller noise levels radiated were low comparing to other marine activities and at the study site the attenuation of the sound is greater until 300 m far from the device (Cruz et al., 2015). Lastly, underwater noise levels recorded from the Wavestar WEC during the operation phase were so low that would barely be audible to marine mammals hence the likelihood of impact was minimal, even though most moving parts are placed above water (Tougaard, 2015).

Despite the minor level magnitude attributed from noise pollution effects in the available data, an overall evaluation ranging from minor to moderate is qualified to construction activities and negligible to moderate for operation period, since there are still many uncertainties about the assessment of risk levels for behavioural disturbance, masking and physical damage, not only for marine mammals, but also for fishes, marine invertebrates and birds.

4.2.4 Electromagnetic Fields Disturbance

The ability to sense and respond to EMFs is characteristic to many taxonomic groups of marine organisms, that either sense magnetic fields (B fields), electric fields (E fields) or both. Taxa that have been determined to be magneto-sensitive are generally those that undertake large-scale migrations or use Earth's natural geomagnetic fields for orientation, comprising cetaceans, diadromous fish (e.g. salmon, eel) and crustaceans (Kirshvnik, 1997). In terms of electroreception, elasmobranchs (sharks, rays and skates) and agnathans (lampreys) have the sensory apparatus to detect and respond to electric fields to detect very low-frequency bioelectric fields emitted by prey or mates and for orientation (Collin and Whitehead, 2004). Additionally, some species use electric fields behaviourally (Iglesias et al., 2018).

All WEC devices possess a variety of EMF emitting sources through submarine cables involved in transmitting electrical energy from the device to land substations. The electrical currents transmitted in undersea cables induce electromagnetic fields, and these fields may affect marine organisms (Öhman et al. 2007; Greaves et al., 2016). Industry standard cables effectively shield against direct electric emissions but cannot completely shield against the magnetic component. The leakage of B fields results in induced E fields adjacent to the cable independent of burial, as a result of magnetic properties (CMACS, 2003). Freeman et al. (2013) highlighted that cables suspended in the mid-water column (e.g. those associated with Pelamis Wave Power) potentially create larger EMF emissions than devices that have buried cables. In contrast, Oyster (Aquamarine Power 2011) does not have any EMF issues, since it has no subsea associated cabling.

Benthic and demersal species are potentially more likely to be exposed to higher field strengths from buried cables than pelagic species. In any case, EMFs can cause some species-specific responses. However, to date,

there are not enough evidence to determine if there are significant, negative or positive impacts on the receptor species. Furthermore, it cannot be ruled out if there are any longer term physiological, biochemical or behavioural effects as a consequence of interaction between organisms and EMF at different developmental stages of life (Hutchison et al., 2018).

4.3 Socioeconomic Factors

Nearshore ecosystems provide a wide range of services to human society. The introduction of a proposed MRE device raises several socioeconomic effects, including employment and regional income enhancement, sea and land use conflicts with other coastal users, aesthetics and local patrimony pressures, and implications to socio-cultural, touristic and recreation activities. Table 4.5 presents a matrix of the potential socioeconomic impacts of nearshore energy devices, and a detailed interpretation is presented below based on the following receptors: local communities, archaeology and protected sites, landscape and seascape, and economic activities (comprising enterprises such as fisheries, navigation and aquaculture).

4.3.1 Local communities

At national level, the deployment of a WEC will provide valuable experience and know-how required for companies to become integral parts of the supply chain for the emerging ocean energy sector. A local project combined with operational experience and general know-how can stimulate the formulation of knowledge centres and technology hubs for an export industry. Opinion studies conducted in Europe and the United States indicate that the public is generally supportive of developing alternative energy sources (Ladenburg, 2008; Dong Energy et al., 2006). For the current analysis, this receptor aggregates local economy development, tourism, recreation and amenity sea users.

Firstly, some coastal restricted areas will be established to carry on construction activities, such as the cable laying to the onshore substation. These interdiction zones will temporally prevent the practice of surf and beach leisure sports. In addition, the works for the cable path and the substation itself may disturb residents by increase of noise and traffic. On the other side, the creation of jobs destined to transport operations, placement of equipment and possible manufacture of some components contributes positively to regional sector development and economy.

During the operation phase, a period for public disclosure about the project might open, providing the opportunity for environmental education and awareness campaigns, appealing for energy politics and actions against climate change. These effects are, however, hard to predict. On the other hand, the functioning of the device will bring energy supply to the public electricity network. Ultimately, the interdiction of the area for the practice of surf might be reduced due to the alteration that the development might employ in the wave climate, though this effect is hard to predict without wave parameters' measures during operation of the device. Accidental events should also be considered, as local beach users might be affected by chemical, oil or fuel spills that contaminate water quality. Plus, the presence of any equipment or structural component adrift might increase the risk of injury to sea users.

In the decommissioning phase, a reversion of the negative impacts stated during the operation of the device is expected e.g., the potential conflict of uses with the surfing community. Once again, a demand for job opportunities might emerge for the transport and dismantlement of the device and structural components.

4.3.2 Archaeology and protected sites

A preliminary project site survey should inform the eventual presence of cultural patrimony sites. In case of identification, any intrusive action in land or submersed sites of archaeological or biodiversity conservation interest might put these preserved areas at risk. These negative impacts could be recognized as very significant, but project developers usually manage to avoid any disturbance to sites of relevant consideration, hence the difficult prediction of the impact.

4.3.3 Landscape and seascape

Every MRE project presents terrestrial and maritime space components, therefore potential impacts on the visual amenity in natural sceneries might overcome. A preliminary site survey, baseline seascape, landscape and visual assessment must be undertaken in the baseline study for the project site, so that relevant and historic interest point views are identified.

Construction is the stage that carries the most significant visual impact, though temporary, since terrestrial works might disrupt landscapes of relevant interest and the increase in vessel activity disturbs the natural amenity of the sea scenery. After installation, project components might still be observed from the coast, especially if it is located nearshore, damaging the concept of “natural beaches”, if present in the test site. Factors that influence structures sight include colour, orientation, structural design, materials etc. After decommissioning, landscape and seascape would recover their natural heritage scenery. Overall, these impacts are deemed with low magnitude, as the project developers usually appeal for the avoidance of areas with historic or cultural interest, but if this is not possible, it may be considered as very significant impact.

4.3.4 Economic activities

The main economic activities considered in the matrix are navigation, fisheries and tourism. Coastal developers fight for coastal space to progress their industry sector. Enterprises such as aquaculture, offshore wind power and wave power demand much more marine space, in competition to traditional sea users like fisheries and navigation (Engle, 2009; Simas et al., 2013; Draget, 2014). Generally, fishing and navigation are the main socioeconomic enterprises identified near wave exploitation sites, therefore the introduction of a WEC device or array will affect their normal operation. Moreover, a chance for ecotourism development and other leisure activities will also support the regional economy, as well as the opportunity for new business and company's creation.

The conflict of maritime space use begins when exclusion zones are created for the safe deployment of devices, with the restriction of other activities in a delimited area. In addition, the fishery sector might suffer more with permanent loss of fishing grounds and potentially ground-based fisheries due to construction works. During construction phase, the sea use is completely interdicted to avoid vessel accidents. In post-deployment phase, the exclusion zones are still implemented, so the fishing sector remains with loss of exploitation areas although sea users may already surround the restricted zones.

In case of chemical, oil or fuel spills, potential contamination in existent nearby aquaculture facilities might occur, affecting the production, hence food resource for the population. The accidental loss of equipment or structural device's component may also damage fishing nets or aquaculture cages and provide risk to navigation. On decommissioning phase, a restoration of the excluded zones is predicted, allowing for the total use of marine space by other coastal users.

Table 4.5: Summary Impact Matrix for potential socioeconomic impacts of nearshore installations. M: Impact magnitude; NK: no anticipated key effect; ?: depends on site specific features.

Socioeconomic Effects			Receptor							
Development phase	Activity	Stressor	Local Communities		Archaeology Protected Sites		Landscape Seascape	Economic activities		
			Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M	Key Effect	M
Preparation	Surveying	Sampling; Vessel activity and sonar/ seismic surveys	Marine spatial restrictions for sea users	M	Potential disruption of preserved traces	M	NK	NK	Marine spatial restrictions for sea users	M
			Noise disturbance	M					Potential disruption to inshore/shoreline-based fisheries	M
	Site preparation	Dredging activities	Marine spatial restrictions for sea users	M	Potential disruption of preserved traces	?	NK	Marine spatial restrictions for sea users	M	
Construction	Transport of wave device and support structures	Vessel activity and noise; Presence of machinery/equipment	Noise disturbance	M	Potential disruption of preserved traces	M	NK	Marine spatial restrictions for sea users	M	
	Installation of wave device and support structures	Installation of WEC; Works onshore	Interdiction to sea use for locals; Local disturbance; Noise disturbance	M	Potential disruption of preserved traces	?	NK	Marine spatial restrictions for sea users (e.g. loss of fishery areas)	M	
Operation	Device deployment	WEC device and support structures; Energy extraction	Potential struggle for the practice of surf sports	?	NK		Loss of shoreline amenities; Visual Impact	M	Marine spatial restrictions for sea users (e.g. loss of fishery areas)	M
			NK		NK		NK	Promotion of leisure activities (e.g. recreational scuba diving) and ecotourism	M	
		Renewable electricity production	Clean energy supply (avoidance of GHG emissions); Education campaigns; Ecotourism; Blue	M	NK		NK	NK	NK	M

			Economy development						
Decommissioning	Removal of device and structural components	Vessel activity; Presence of machinery/equipment	Marine spatial restrictions for sea users		Potential disruption of preserved traces	?	NK		Marine spatial restrictions for sea users
All development phases (accidental events)	All project activities	Need for manpower, expertise and services	Employment enhancement		NK		NK		New opportunities for company creation and development
		Project development in the region	Perception of energy cost reduction; Reduction of fossil fuel dependence and tackling climate change		NK		NK		
			Negative perception of the effect of local environmental impacts		NK		NK	Negative perception of the effect of environmental impacts on commercial activities	
	Chemical/oil/fuel spill	Chemical and oil pollution	Potential pollution of public spaces (e.g. beach, rocky shorelines)		Potential pollution of sites with relevant interest	?	Visual impact		Potential disruption to economic activities
	Loss of equipment/structural components	Drifting/sinking of equipment	Visual impact; Risk of collision with sea users		Potential disruption of preserved traces	?	Visual Impact		Hazard to navigation; Potential disruption to economic activities

5 ENVIRONMENTAL MITIGATION MEASURES FOR WAVE ENERGY PROJECTS

From a general point of view and for all stages of development, any activity should be planned to take place only when the developer is confident that there is no risk of bad weather and/or sea conditions and should avoid, wherever possible, sensitive, protected and/or recreational areas. The activity should also be scheduled outside periods of seasonal migrations, and/or breeding seasons of targeted species.

A list of mitigation measures is presented in Table 5.1 for the impacts classified, under Chapter 4, as negligible, minor, moderate and major, considering each project phase. It is important to note that it was assumed that mitigation measures for the decommissioning phase are comparable to the ones suggested for the construction phase since the key effects are very similar.

Table 5.1: Mitigation measures.

Phase	Stressor	Receptors	Mitigation Measures
All	Vessel activity	Water column Fish and turtles Marine mammals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low vessel speed when going to assemble the site, giving an opportunity to organisms to evade the area - Block the use of the area to other nearshore users, to minimize vessel traffic; - Contracted vessels should carry spill mop up kits or material to stop accidental spills and contain the discharged substance on the water surface.
Preparation	Dredging activities	Water column Seabed Benthic communities Fish and turtles Marine mammals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selection of mining areas that cause the least environmental damage and analysis of sediment quality and contamination level in surrounding areas prior to dredging; - Reduce the seabed area to be cleared and restrict it to immediate vicinity of the project; - Mathematical model simulations, to predict impacts; - Eco-efficient surface mining, by establishing a limit depth to mine or creation of pits; - Remediation procedures for contaminated sediment e.g., mechanical mixing and aeration; - Usage of silt screens, to limit the dispersion of suspended sediments.
	Sonar / Seismic surveys	Fish and turtles Marine mammals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Soft start ('ramp up'); - Delineation of a safety zone, where a temporary shut down or power reduction is triggered in case of observation of cetaceans within that area.

Phase	Stressor	Receptors	Mitigation Measures
Construction and Decommissioning	Installation of WEC device	Seabed Water column Benthic communities Fish and turtles Marine mammals Birds Local communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Works carried out on the seabed should be limited to the minimum required; - If possible, the various types of anchors (rock, latching and stabilization) should be chosen based on a minimum practical depth into the sediment, thus limiting the volume of drill cuttings discharged to the environment and the seabed morphology disruption; - Onshore, reduce the cable path to minimum areas; - Disclose the calendar of intervention operations and a plan of restricted areas to the local communities, particularly to fishermen and shipping operators; - Seek labor work and material acquisition within the local community.
	Pile driving activities		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce sound pressure levels using pile caps and vibratory hammers; - Attenuate the produced sound using bubble curtains, confined bubble curtains, bubble sleeves, hydro sound dampers or de-watered cofferdams.
	Installation of EMFs	Fish and turtles Marine mammals Local communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Avoidance of sensitive, protected and recreational areas.
Operation	Presence of the device	Benthic communities Fish and turtles Marine mammals Birds Local communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Removal of invasive or exotic species; - Usage of non-toxic anti-biofouling paints; - Delineation of a safety zone, where a temporary shut down or power reduction is triggered in case of observation of cetaceans within that area; - Maintenance of signaling devices, on land and sea, of the restricted area, - Promote environmental awareness in the region.

6 ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING OF WAVE ENERGY PROJECTS

Monitoring is an important step of the EIA process to follow up the effects of impacts as well as to monitor mitigation measures efficiency. The interpretation and evaluation of the outcomes from monitoring results will support the elaboration of a new mitigation plan that will better adjust the environmental system and the goals set forth by the AM process. The identification of the relevant parameters for impacts and mitigation measures follow up through monitoring is then key to optimize the environmental management system. The comprehensive literature review under this work allowed the compilation of several parameters that are usually measured during monitoring activities to evaluate wave energy effects during all phases of the project development and for the impacts classified in the literature as negligible, minor, moderate and major (Chapter 4). These are presented on Table 6.1.

Table 6.1: Monitoring parameters for relevant receptors.

Factor	Receptors	Parameters
Physical Factors	Hydrodynamic System	Wave climate (height, period, mean direction and directional spreading), currents (speed, direction and velocity profile along the water column), turbulence, bathymetry
	Water Column	Turbidity levels, temperature, salinity, water depth, Chlorophyll <i>a</i> , dissolved oxygen levels, nutrients and contaminants content
	Seabed	Sediment composition and granulometry, sediment transport, contaminants content
	Shoreline	Erosion/deposition patterns, shoreline morphology
Biological Factors	Benthic Community	Species composition and abundance, distribution, density, diversity and dominance structure and percentage of coverage, presence of invasive species
	Fish & Turtles	Species composition (and presence/absence only for marine mammals) and abundance, distribution, density and diversity
	Marine Mammals	
	Birds	
Socioeconomic Factors	Local Communities	Number of direct and indirect jobs created (quantifying highly specialized ones), level of public acceptance, identification of relevant stakeholders, quantification of GHG emissions avoided
	Archaeological sites	Archaeological site identification
	Landscape and Seascape	Visual perception/impact
	Economic Activities	Overlap with other marine uses (marine spatial planning analysis), number of new businesses created, identification of relevant stakeholders

7 THE EIA MODEL

The standard method for EIA of nearshore based energy devices has been developed considering the EIA general approach shown in Figure 1.1 and focusing on potential impacts' identification and analysis, mitigation and monitoring to validate the impacts' analysis. This method is intended to be a guide for managers and regulators on the identification of the most significant environmental and socioeconomic impacts of a project, definition of mitigation measures and planning of monitoring protocols and techniques. The method is to be applied on a case-by-case basis i.e. considering the project specific characteristics and site environmental conditions.

The EIA model is based on the identification and evaluation of the potential impacts of wave energy devices presented in the previous chapter, using the summary impact matrices (Table 4.3, Table 4.4 and Table 4.5). From here, a set of parameters and a set of mitigation measures taken from literature was then linked to the all relevant receptors. At the end, a decision tree method for the identification of the most appropriate monitoring techniques and protocols was delineated based on the parameters the user chooses for each receptor. These decision tree structure was adapted for the method developed by Shumchenia et al. (2012). The final output of the model is a set of monitoring plans for all the relevant receptors identified per development phase

To reduce environmental and socioeconomic potential effects and adjust the assessment during the EIA process, an AM procedure is adopted in this model to consider changes in the project impacts and their respective mitigation measures' as well as the adaptation of the monitoring plan, according to monitoring results. The selected monitoring techniques aim to assess the impacts magnitude classification and monitor the effectiveness of implemented mitigation measures, to update, if required, the impacts' magnitude classification, define a new set of mitigation measures and help adapting the monitoring plan.

Figure 7.1 summarizes the steps of the proposed model, which starts with impacts prioritization (Step 1), followed by the selection of mitigation measures (Step 2) and finally by the identification of monitoring techniques and protocols (Step 3) considering project features and existing information on site environmental conditions. The EIA model steps are detailed in the sections below.

Figure 7.1: Flowchart of the proposed model.

7.1 Step 1: Impacts identification and evaluation

Step 1 consists of adapting the impacts classification presented in the summary impacts’ matrices (Chapter 4) according to the project features and environmental sensitiveness of the site. This allows impacts prioritization, classifying them according to the EMEC’s classification ranking (**Error! Reference source not found.** and Table 4.2) for each phase of the project development, in a case by case analysis.

7.2 Step 2: Mitigation measures listing

Following the identification, evaluation and prioritization of the project key impacts, the list of mitigation measures needs to be identified to prevent, minimize and compensate for those negative effects of the project development. Different mitigation measures are needed depending on specific interactions of the project components with the environmental receptors. Step 2 of the EIA model consists in assigning mitigation measures to the impacts that have been prioritised under Step 1. A final matrix containing the stressors, receptors, impacts and selected mitigation measures is generated to inform Step 3 on the effectiveness of these measures follow up through monitoring.

7.3 Step 3: Monitoring protocols planning

The last step comprises the identification of the monitoring protocols and techniques to be carried out. A decision tree was developed to serve as decision-support tool, to help managers and regulators determining which monitoring techniques need to be included in the monitoring plan.

The monitoring framework developed in this report was adapted from the method developed by Shumchenia et al. (2012) and includes the use of the environmental parameters presented in Chapter 6. To help the manager or regulator use this method, a decision tree was developed to set the most appropriate monitoring techniques (listed in Table 7.1) in each stage of development. Three distinct decision trees were developed for the physical (Table 7.2) Table 7.2 - Decision tree for selection of monitoring techniques for the physical factors., biological (Table 7.3) and socioeconomic factors (Table 7.4). The user is guided through these decision trees by answering a set of questions on the receptor, parameter and stage of development towards the monitoring protocols that determine the monitoring plan across all the receptors considered.

The monitoring methodology can change considerably depending on the stage of development being analysed regarding its schedule and planning. Thus, after the identification of the monitoring techniques and protocols per parameter and receptor, the model will provide information on the monitoring planning and schedule specific to each development phase considering the parameters monitoring spatial coverage, duration and frequency.

Table 7.1: Monitoring techniques/protocols.

Monitoring Techniques/protocols	Code	Monitoring Techniques/protocols	Code
Acoustic doppler current profiler (ADCP)	1	Radar observations (birds)	14
Active acoustic – sonars	2	ROVs, underwater cameras	15
Aerial photographs	3	Sampling collection and analysis techniques	16
Analytical methods (e.g. econometric models)	4	Satellite images	17
Conductivity, Temperature, Depth (CTD)	5	Secchi disk method	18
Desk based analysis	6	Sonar and LIDAR techniques	19
Dive surveys	7	Spectrophotometry, high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) or fluorometry	20
Geographic Information Systems (GIS)	8	Telemetry tags	21
Hydrophones	9	Temperature sensors	22
In situ multiparametric probes	10	Turbidity meters	23
Observation surveys	11	Use of models	24
Participatory methods (e.g. questionnaires/surveys, dialogue methods)	12	Wave measure buoys	25
Passive acoustic – C-Pods	13	Winkler method and oxygen sensors	26

Table 7.2 - Decision tree for selection of monitoring techniques for the physical factors.

<i>The receptor is</i>		
	Hydrodynamic System	Go to A
	Water Column	Go to B
	Seabed	Go to C
	Shoreline	Go to D
(A) The parameter is	Wave climate	1, 25
	Currents	1
	Turbulence	1
	Bathymetry	2, 19
(B) The parameter is	Turbidity levels	18, 23
	Temperature, salinity and water depth	6, 10, 22
	Chlorophyll <i>a</i>	20
	Dissolved oxygen levels	10, 26
	Nutrient and contaminants content	10
(C) The parameter is	Sediment composition and granulometry	16
	Sediment transport	23
	Contaminants content	16
(D) The parameter is	Erosion/deposition patterns	3, 17, 24
	Shoreline morphology	3, 17, 24

Table 7.3 - Decision tree for selection of monitoring techniques for the biological factors.

<i>The receptor is</i>		
	Benthic Community	Go to A
	Fish & Turtles	Go to B
	Marine Mammals	Go to C
	Birds	Go to D
(A) The parameter is	Species Composition, Abundance and Density	7, 15, 16
	Species Distribution and % of coverage	7, 15
	Species Diversity and Dominance Structure	16
	Presence of invasive species	7, 15, 16
(B) The parameter is	Species Composition	6
	Species Abundance	2, 6, 15
	Species Distribution	6, 21
	Species Density	15
	Species Diversity	6, 15
(C) The parameter is	Species Composition/Diversity and presence/absence	11, 13, 15
	Species Abundance and Density	11, 15
	Species Distribution	11, 13, 15, 21
(D) The parameter is	Species Composition and Diversity	11
	Species Abundance and Density	11, 14
	Species Distribution	11, 14, 21

Table 7.4 - Decision tree for selection of monitoring techniques for the socioeconomic factors.

<i>The receptor is</i>		
	Local Communities	Go to A
	Archaeological Sites	Go to B
	Landscape and Seascape	Go to C
	Economic Activities	Go to D
(A) The parameter is	Number of direct and indirect jobs created	6
	Level of public acceptance	12
	Identification of relevant stakeholders	6, 12
	Quantification of GHG emissions avoided	4
(B) The parameter is	Archaeological site identification	8
(C) The parameter is	Visual perception/impact	6, 12
(D) The parameter is	Overlap with other marine uses	8
	Identification of relevant stakeholders	6, 12
	Number of new businesses created	6

8 CONCLUSIONS

EIA processes and knowledge acquisition on the devices interaction with the marine environment represent crucial aspects when approaching consenting/permitting processes. This study presents a model of EIA for nearshore wave energy devices that helps the user on the identification and classification of the most significant key effects and on the delineation of a set of mitigation of monitoring activities by using an AM approach. It would be inefficient to monitor every interaction that could potentially result in an impact. As such, although there are several potential impacts associated to this type of projects, a prioritization of the most significant impacts was carried out.

In suggesting a set of monitoring objectives, there was an attempt to account for variability in regions, target species, etc, but decisions about the most appropriate monitoring activities will still be based on site and project specificities and thus will have to be made on a case-by-case basis.

The implementation of an AM approach in the MRE industry may face some challenges, including a lack of legislation and regulations requiring AM in most countries, and potential increased costs to the project for AM implementation. The early stage of wave energy technologies lacks information on the impacts on the environment and thus the decision is risk based relying on the implementation of mitigation measures and on the results of monitoring activities. This approach should nevertheless be applied to all MRE projects, as it has potential to help them move forward in the face of uncertainty and learn from previous developments.

Given the lack of EIAs for wave energy devices, and particularly for nearshore projects, it was difficult to gather all the information needed. Nevertheless, the method developed under this study represents a significant step towards the standardization of EIA for nearshore wave energy devices. The data collected for the elaboration of this framework provides a means for deepening our knowledge of the potential environmental and socioeconomic impacts of nearshore wave energy projects, allowing regulators and managers for better decision-making. Finally, this report sets the basis for the development of a decision-making tool on the delineation of best monitoring activities schedule and scenarios to optimize time and costs, which will later be validated through its application to the final MegaRoller design.

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